

A Validated Framework for Far-Field Noise Prediction of Containerized BESS: From Optimized Sound Power Measurement to Simulation

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of large-scale Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) stations poses significant environmental noise challenges, necessitating accurate far-field noise prediction in the early design stages. The accuracy of these predictions is critically dependent on precise sound source data of individual BESS containers. This paper presents a novel framework using a mobile robotic arm to perform high-resolution sound intensity scanning (ISO 9614-2) across the container's surfaces. This method enables the precise identification of noise-contributing areas, yielding a high-resolution source map that is used to create a high-fidelity area source model in CadnaA. The model's predictions were validated against on-site measurements at a receiver 71.2 m from the source, achieving a prediction error in overall Sound Pressure Level (SPL) of only 1.5 dB. In contrast, a conventional model based on the ISO 3744 standard yielded a prediction error of 7.5 dB in the same scenario. The proposed framework thus significantly enhances noise prediction accuracy, providing a more reliable tool for designing effective noise control measures for BESS facilities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global transition towards renewable energy has significantly accelerated the deployment of BESS [1,2], with rapid expansions of utility-scale facilities playing a pivotal role in modern grid stabilization [3,4]. However, the proliferation of these large-scale facilities, often located near residential areas, has introduced significant environmental noise challenges. Consequently, balancing the demand for sustainable energy with community tranquility and regulatory compliance has emerged as a critical industry challenge [5].

In contrast to the mature Noise, Vibration, and Harshness (NVH) domains in other industries [6–14], comprehensive acoustic research specifically targeting BESS is still developing. While some literature has explored the use of acoustic signals as early warning mechanisms for thermal runaway events [15], research addressing environmental noise has highlighted critical modeling deficiencies. For instance, recent studies have shown that traditional simplified models—such as a point source that neglects the BESS container's own body—fail to account for complex on-site barrier and diffraction effects, leading to significant over-predictions of far-field noise [16].

The primary obstacle to accurate prediction, as emphasized in recent works [4, 16], is the severe lack of detailed, spatially-resolved noise emission data. Equipment suppliers often provide only a

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single, overall sound power value, treating component-level emissions as proprietary. This data scarcity forces modelers to rely on unverified assumptions. For example, some studies have adopted conservative, worst-case operational scenarios (e.g., 100% fan speeds) and assumed a simplified even energy split between intake and exhaust vents to construct area source models [4]. Other attempts to use area source models did not specify the spatial distribution of sound power in detail, limiting their applicability [16]. These simplifications inherently fail to capture the container's critical role as a local noise barrier, which significantly alters sound radiation patterns [16].

Precise environmental noise prediction for a BESS station requires accurate source modeling, which depends on exact sound power level (SWL), radiating areas, and component locations. Traditionally, SWL is measured using the sound pressure method (ISO 3744) [17]. However, its application for on-site container acceptance is highly challenging due to unavoidable ambient background noise [16]. More importantly, ISO 3744 provides only a single overall value, failing to localize sources or provide the detailed geometric sound distribution required for the advanced area-source models that recent studies advocate for [16]. Alternatively, the sound intensity method (ISO 9614-1 [18] or ISO 9614-2 [19]) offers significant advantages by isolating specific surfaces and rejecting steady background noise [20].

Despite these advantages, the massive dimensions of a BESS container render manual intensity scanning under ISO 9614-2 extremely labor-intensive and prone to poor precision due to inconsistent sweep speed and probe distance. To overcome these limitations and directly address the critical gap in source data, we propose a novel automated measurement approach. We developed a movable robotic arm system engineered to execute ISO 9614-2 scanning procedures automatically. By dividing the container surface into 76 distinct sub-areas, the robotic system performs sequential, highly repeatable scans to determine both the SWL and the spatial energy distribution for each face. This high-resolution data directly enables the creation of high-fidelity area source models that accurately account for the container's self-shielding and diffraction effects, thus filling the modeling gap identified by current literature [4, 16]. All measurements and analyses in this study are bounded within the probe's effective frequency range (160 Hz to 6300 Hz 1/3 octave bands), corresponding to its 12 mm spacer.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 details the experimental setup. Section 3 describes the measurement procedures and data comparison against relevant standards. Section 4 presents the generation of acoustic heat maps, compares far-field predictions from our detailed model against a simplified ISO 3744-based model, and validates them with on-site measurements. Finally, Section 5 concludes with a discussion of the method's feasibility, advantages, limitations, and future work.

2. METHODOLOGY AND MEASUREMENT RESULTS

This section details the experimental methodology and the resulting acoustic characterization of the BESS container. A dual-approach strategy was employed: first, a benchmark SWL was established using the conventional sound pressure method (ISO 3744); second, a high-resolution sound intensity mapping was executed using a robotic scanning system (ISO 9614-2). The primary results of these measurements, which serve as the foundation for the simulation model, are presented at the end of this section.

2.1. Test Site and Subject

All tests were performed at an outdoor, open-field test site with a hard, reflective ground surface (asphalt) that approximated a hemi-free field. These conditions were chosen to ensure stable and

repeatable noise emissions, allowing for a direct comparison between the two measurement methods. The layout of the test site, including the central BESS container, the far-field monitoring points on the right, and the surrounding environment, is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Google Earth Site Map Showing the BESS Container Location and Far-field Measurement Point.

The test subject was a standard containerized BESS unit (rated at 3.0 MW / 6.0 MWh), with external dimensions of 6058 mm (L) x 2400 mm (W) x 2989 mm (H), as shown in Figure 2. The primary noise sources were identified as the openings of the cooling system, specifically the air inlets on the 'Front' side and the exhausts on the 'Left' side. However, the entire container acts as a radiating body. To ensure a comprehensive assessment, both measurement methods were configured to encompass all five radiating surfaces (Front, Back, Left, Right, and Top), excluding the Bottom.

Figure 2: Photograph of the BESS Container

2.2. Benchmark Measurement: Sound Pressure Method (ISO 3744)

2.2.1. Experimental Setup

Following ISO 3744, a measurement surface was established at a distance of 1 m from the reference parallelepiped of the BESS container. A 48-microphone array was distributed over the top and four vertical sides of this surface (Figure 3) to determine the spatial average SPL. Additionally, a dedicated reference point was positioned 1 m from the center of the primary cooling exhaust. This point served to monitor operational stability and for comparison with the ISO 9614-2 scan data. All measurements were conducted in low ambient noise to minimize background interference.

Figure 3: BESS Container Instrumented for Sound Power Testing via the ISO 3744 Method.

2.2.2. Instrumentation

The SPLs were captured simultaneously by 49 ICP microphones (PCB 378B02) connected to a data acquisition system (SIEMENS LMS SCM2E09). Before and after the measurement campaign, all microphones were calibrated using a Larson Davis CAL200 sound calibrator.

2.3. High-Resolution Measurement: Robotic Sound Intensity Scanning (ISO 9614-2)

2.3.1. System Configuration

A six-axis industrial robotic arm on a mobile platform was used to manipulate a G.R.A.S. 50AI-L sound intensity probe. The probe was mounted on a custom extension bracket to minimize self-noise from the manipulator (Figure 4). A 12 mm spacer between the phase-matched microphones defined an effective frequency range from the 160 Hz to 6300 Hz 1/3 octave bands. The probe was connected to a SIEMENS LMS SCM2E09 data acquisition system and calibrated using a G.R.A.S. 51AB sound probe calibrator.

Figure 4: Schematic of the Automated Sound Intensity Scanning Procedure Using the Six-axis Robotic Arm: (a) Scanning Vertical Surface; (b) Scanning Horizontal Surface.

2.3.2. Measurement Procedure

To ensure comprehensive coverage, the main radiating surfaces of the BESS container were discretized into a total of 76 rectangular sub-areas (Figure 5a). These sub-areas were grouped into larger scan zones defined by the robot's reach: 600 mm (W) x 1500 mm (H) for vertical surfaces and 600 mm (W) x 1200 mm (L) for the top surface. This segmentation strategy accommodated the robotic arm's workspace while ensuring an acoustically clear path for the intensity probe, preventing the robot arm from causing acoustic shadowing or reflections along the probe's measurement axis. The operating parameters were strictly controlled, with the cooling fans set to

66% Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM) and both the compressor and water pump stabilized at 5400 RPM.

For each sub-area, the robot executed [a raster scan in two orthogonal directions sequentially] (Figure 5b) at a speed of 100 mm/s. During the scan, the probe was maintained at a constant distance of 100 mm from the surface with a line spacing of 100 mm. The sound intensity for each sub-area was then determined by averaging the results from the two orthogonal passes. This automated, dual-scan methodology ensures the consistency and repeatability critical for high-precision sound power determination.

Figure 5: Schematic of the Sound Intensity Measurement Segmentation and Scanning Strategy: (a) Division of the BESS Surfaces; (b) the Two-Pass Orthogonal Raster Scan Path.

2.4. Sound Power Measurement Results

2.4.1. Overall SWL Validation

To validate the automated sound intensity method (ISO 9614-2), its results were benchmarked against the established sound pressure method (ISO 3744). First, operational stability was confirmed, with the reference SPL showing minimal variation: 75.3 dB(A) during the ISO 9614-2 scan versus 75.4 dB(A) during the ISO 3744 measurement. The primary result shows the overall A-weighted SWL from the intensity method was 84.7 dB(A), in excellent agreement with the 85.8 dB(A) from the pressure method. This small discrepancy of 1.1 dB validates the accuracy of the automated approach.

2.4.2. Spectral Characteristics and Source Localization

Figure 6 compares the 1/3 octave band sound power spectra obtained from the sound intensity and sound pressure methods. The spectra exhibited strong agreement (within 3 dB) across the mid-to-high frequency range, which is characteristic of the BESS cooling system's acoustic signature. However, a notable deviation was observed at lower frequencies, with a discrepancy peaking at approximately 5 dB in the 200 Hz 1/3 octave band. This low-frequency divergence is likely attributed to near-field aerodynamic effects (pseudo sound) influencing the sound intensity probe. Due to the close measurement distance (100 mm) at high-airflow locations like inlets and outlets, pressure fluctuations unrelated to acoustic propagation can contaminate the intensity measurement, a phenomenon to which the far-field sound pressure method is less susceptible.

The primary outcome of the robotic scanning is a high-resolution sound intensity map of the BESS container's radiating surfaces, as depicted in Figure 7. The map clearly identifies the primary acoustic "hot spots," which correspond directly to the cooling system outlets. While dominated by fan noise, these regions also integrate significant contributions from other internal components such

as compressors and pumps. This level of detailed spatial source characterization is unattainable with the spatially-averaged sound pressure method and is critical for developing a physically accurate, non-uniform area-source model for far-field prediction.

Figure 6: 1/3 Octave Band Chart Comparing the SWL Spectra from ISO 3744 and ISO 9614-2.

Figure 7: Sound Intensity Maps Illustrating the Spatial Distribution of Noise from the BESS Container: (a) Left-Front View; (b) Right-Back View.

2.4.3. Dominant Source Contribution Analysis

The high-resolution sound intensity data facilitates a quantitative, rank-ordered analysis of the primary noise-radiating surfaces. Guided by the sound intensity map (Figure 7), a targeted analysis was performed to isolate the dominant source regions. The six most acoustically active sub-areas on the 'Left' side (out of eight total) and the six most active on the 'Front' side (out of twenty) were identified (specifically, sub-areas #1-3, 5-7 and #8-10, 18-20, respectively, per the numbering scheme in Figure 4). These 12 sub-areas directly correspond to the cooling system's main outlets and inlets.

Table 1: Breakdown of Sound Power Contribution by Surface Region

Surface Region	No. of Sub-areas	SWL (dB(A))	Power Contribution (%)
Left Side	6	82.5	61.3
Front Side	6	80.2	35.8
Subtotal	12	84.5	97.1

All Other	64	69.3	2.9
Total	76	84.7	100

The analysis reveals a high concentration of acoustic energy in the intake and exhaust regions, with just 12 sub-areas contributing 97.1% of the total radiated energy (Table 1). Crucially, this energy is unequally distributed, as the exhaust side (61.3%) dominates the intake side (35.8%). This finding not only challenges the common assumption of uniform source distribution but also enables the development of a simplified yet accurate acoustic model focused exclusively on these dominant areas. Such a targeted approach can significantly improve computational efficiency with minimal impact on prediction accuracy, a principle that underpins the modeling strategy presented in Section 3.

3. DEVELOPMENT OF FAR-FIELD NOISE MODELS

3.1. Modelling Software and Environmental Setup

Noise propagation was predicted according to the ISO 9613-2[21]: "Attenuation of Sound During Propagation Outdoors" standard. The calculations were executed using the commercial acoustic modeling software CadnaA (Version 2026 MR1). The model geometry was constructed based on site surveys and satellite imagery, incorporating the BESS container, nearby buildings, and key terrain features, as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Site Model Based on Google Earth

3.2. Simulation Parameters

To ensure a direct and fair comparison between the two modeling approaches, a consistent set of environmental and physical parameters was applied across all simulations.

- Atmospheric Conditions: A temperature of 10°C and a relative humidity of 70% were assumed. These conditions represent a conservative scenario with minimal atmospheric sound absorption, as prescribed by ISO 9613-2 for worst-case analysis.
- Terrain and Ground Effect: The ground within the facility was modeled as acoustically hard (asphalt, Ground Factor $G=0$), while surrounding areas with vegetation were modeled as porous ($G=1$).
- Reflections and Diffractions: The BESS container itself, along with adjacent buildings, were modeled as solid obstacles. Third-order reflections and diffractions were enabled to account for sound bouncing off surfaces and bending over edges, which is critical in complex industrial environments.

3.3. Source Definition for Modelling Scenarios

The fundamental difference between the two models lies in how the BESS container as a noise source is defined, as illustrated schematically in Figure 9. The acoustic input data for each model, presented in 1/3 octave bands, are detailed in Table 2.

- Point Source: The BESS container was modeled as a single, omnidirectional point source located at the geometric center of its roof. The sound power spectrum of the source was derived from the aggregate measurement results according to the ISO 3744 standard.
- Area Source: Based on the findings in Section 2.4.3, the BESS container was modeled using 12 discrete, planar area sources. These sources were precisely positioned on the model geometry to represent the dominant fan inlets and outlets.

Figure 9: Schematic Illustration of BESS Noise Modeling, (a) Point Source; (b) Area Source.

Table 2: Comparison of Point Source Versus 12 Area Sources (dB(A))

SOURCE TYPE	Octave-Band SWL (dB(A))							Overall SWL (dB(A))
	125	250	500	1000	2000	4000	8000	
	Hz	Hz	Hz	Hz	Hz	Hz	Hz	
Point Source	71.8	78.3	80.5	79.8	78.0	73.0	63.8	85.8
Area Source_Left:1	64.8	68.3	70.6	69.7	66.3	61.9	48.8	75.6
Area Source_Left:2	64.9	70.9	71.8	71.3	68.0	63.6	50.3	77.2
Area Source_Left:3	55.8	64.2	62.8	62.2	54.6	50.9	38.6	68.5
Area Source_Left:5	61.8	67.1	69.7	69.4	67.0	61.6	49.7	75.0
Area Source_Left:6	62.8	69.4	71.3	70.9	68.8	63.2	51.4	76.6
Area Source_Left:7	55.6	62.8	62.8	62.0	57.2	51.3	41.9	68.1
Area Source_Front:8	42.6	49.2	53.2	53.2	49.6	46.2	35.4	58.2

Area Source_Front:9	56.6	60.2	66.1	64.8	61.6	60.1	48.1	70.5
Area Source_Front:10	62.2	66.2	70.5	70.4	68.2	67.4	54.5	76.1
Area Source_Front:18	42.7	49.1	53.1	55.1	49.0	45.7	35.2	58.8
Area Source_Front:19	54.0	61.3	63.4	65.7	62.9	62.3	49.4	70.5
Area Source_Front:20	58.8	65.5	69.3	70.2	69.6	69.0	55.6	76.1

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. 3D Far-Field Noise Prediction

To ensure a direct comparison, a common simulation setup was used: the BESS was elevated on a 100 mm mat, and receivers were placed on a 2000 mm × 2000 mm grid at a 1500 mm height. The baseline point-source model (Fig. 10a) aggregated the total SWL (from ISO 3744) at the roof's geometric center. While computationally efficient, this omnidirectional model failed to capture the directivity of key sources. It showed some self-shielding but could not represent the complex propagation and shadowing caused by the actual source distribution.

In contrast, the high-fidelity area-source model (Fig. 10b) distributed the SWL across 12 discrete surfaces at the BESS ventilation apertures. This accurately captured source directivity, with maximum SPLs localized near the active surfaces. Crucially, this model revealed a pronounced, asymmetrical "shadow zone" caused by the container's own geometry acting as a robust acoustic barrier, a finding confirmed by sensitivity analysis. This demonstrates that modeling discrete surfaces and physical volume is critical for accurately predicting localized acoustic impacts, a task for which the point-source method is fundamentally unsuited.

Figure 10: 3D Far-field Noise Contour Map Prediction: (a) Point Source; (b) Area Source.

4.2. Validation with Experimental Data

To quantitatively evaluate the accuracy of the two simulation methods, the predicted noise levels at a single far-field receiver point were compared with experimental values. This receiver was situated at a distance of 71.2 m from the nearest point of the container. The results, along with the calculated deviations, are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of Predicted Far-field Noise Levels with Test Data.

VALUE TYPE	Octave-Band SPL (dB(A))					Overall SPL (dB(A))
	250Hz	500Hz	1000Hz	2000Hz	4000 Hz	
Measured SPL	35.2	37.5	36.0	37.4	35.4	43.5
Predicted SPL(Point)	29.3	31.1	30.2	27.9	21.3	36
Deviation (Point)	5.9	6.4	5.8	9.5	14.1	7.5
Predicted SPL(Area)	34.8	36.9	36.6	33.7	29.5	42
Deviation (Area)	0.4	0.6	-0.6	3.7	5.9	1.5

The results in Table 3 indicate that the surface source method is in excellent agreement with the experimental data. The prediction error for the far-field overall SPL is merely 1.5 dB, with a maximum error of 5.9 dB in the 4000 Hz octave band and a minimum of only 0.4 dB in the 250 Hz octave band. These results validate the high accuracy of the model. In stark contrast, the point source model exhibits significant deviations, with the overall SPL error reaching 7.5 dB and the maximum error peaking at 14.1 dB in the 4000 Hz octave band. This confirms that for sources with strong directivity, such as the BESS container, a detailed surface source model is necessary for accurate far-field noise prediction.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presents and validates an integrated framework for accurate BESS far-field noise prediction, moving from in-situ sound intensity measurements to CadnaA simulation. By demonstrating a seamless workflow that uses spatially-resolved sound power from key radiating surfaces as area sources—a novel approach for BESS units—this work provides a robust and efficient methodology. This validated process not only enhances modeling fidelity but also drastically reduces measurement time compared to conventional methods without sacrificing accuracy.

The key findings of this study provide critical insights for BESS acoustic modeling. First, the high-resolution sound intensity scanning successfully characterized the BESS acoustic signature, confirming that noise emissions are highly concentrated at the cooling system's intake and exhaust apertures. For the unit under test, the exhaust side was identified as the dominant contributor to the overall sound power, challenging common assumptions of uniform energy distribution. Second, this work demonstrates that by selectively scanning only these key acoustically active regions, an accurate overall SWL can be determined efficiently, provided that ambient noise is sufficiently low. Most importantly, when this detailed source data was used to construct a high-fidelity area-source model, it yielded significantly superior far-field prediction accuracy—achieving a deviation of only 1.5 dB from measured data, a substantial improvement over the 7.5 dB error observed with the conventional point-source model derived from ISO 3744.

Looking forward, this validated simulation model serves as a digital twin for evaluating noise control treatments. We strongly recommend that future BESS simulations adopt the area-source approach for predictive accuracy, with source data acquired via the sound intensity method demonstrated herein. Further research should also focus on refining automated measurement techniques to better isolate source contributions in noisy environments, thereby enhancing source characterization fidelity.

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